

SIMILARITIES AND DIFFERENCES OF SEGMENT DEVICES IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES

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Annotation.

This article compares English vowel and consonant sounds to Uzbek phonemes in order to highlight their unique characteristics. The distinction between a vowel and a consonant is typically thought to be phonemic rather than phonetic. A vowel is produced as a pure musical tone without any obstruction of airflow in the speech tract, which is how a vowel and consonant are distinguished from one another from a phonetic perspective. There are more criteria to identify a vowel from a consonant.

Keywords.

comparative typology, phonetics and phonology, sounds, distinction, category, vowel, consonant, pronunciation.

INTRODUCTION

A branch of linguistics known as comparative typology examines and categorizes languages based on their structural and functional characteristics. Its goal is to outline and clarify the universal traits and structural variety of languages throughout the world. It compares languages without regard to their genetic or structural similarities. There are just a few languages that can be used for comparative typology, and there may only be two at the most.

Every level of the language hierarchy, including the phonetic, phonological, morphological, syntactic, and lexical levels, is addressed by comparative typology. Actually, phonological and phonetic sublevels are found within the phonological level.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Both phonetics and phonology deal with sounds and phonemes, respectively. Alternatively, phonetics deals with human speech sounds, whereas phonology deals with language sounds. Segmental and suprasegmental are the two stages of phonetics and phonology. Phonemes that are realized in diverse speech sounds are studied in segmental phonology. So it may be referred to as phonemics. Prosodics,

or suprasegmental phonology, is the study of the unique characteristics manifested in syllables, stress, and intonation.

As above mentioned, phonemes that are realized in diverse speech sounds are studied in segmental phonology. In this paragraph, we will see English and Uzbek languages **vowel phonemes**, their similarities and differences.

Normal vowel production involves the air stream passing through the nasal, pharyngeal, and oral canals without encountering any impediment. The notes for vowels alter *at the articulatory level in English*:

1. in the stability of articulation
2. in the tongue position
3. in the lip position
4. in their length

In Uzbek they are described:

1. according to the lips position
2. according to the vertical movement of the tongue
3. according to the horizontal movement of the tongue

English has:

- 1.) 10 monophthongs: /i/, /e/, /æ/, /u/, /ʌ/, /ə/, /a:/, /o/, /o:/, /ɜ:/.
- 2.) 8 diphthongs: glides to [i] - /ei/, /oi/, /ai/;
glides to [u] - /au/, /əu/, /uə/;
glides to [ə] - /iə/, /ɛə/
- 3.) 2 diphthongoids: /i:/, /u:/

Thus, the phonemic inventory of English vowels includes 20 phonemes and 6 vowel letters a, i, e, u, o, y, Uzbek has 6 vowel phonemes [i], [e], [a], [u], [o`], [o] and letters i, e, a, u, o', o.

According to *the tongue position* vowels divided into *forward, mid, backward, up, down* in two compared languages.

According to the tongue position English vowels divided into 5 types, but in Uzbek they are in 3 types:

	front vowel	front-retracted vowel	central vowels	back vowels	back-advanced vowel
English	[i: e æ]	[i]	[ʌ ə: ə]	[a: o o: u:]	[u]
Uzbek	[i e]		[o']	[a u o]	

Moving *up and down* in the mouth the tongue may be raised to different height towards the roof of the mouth.

1. When the front or the back of the tongue is raised high towards the palate

the vowel is called *close* in English.

They are - [i: I u u:].

2. When the front or the back of the tongue is as low as possible in the mouth *open* vowels are pronounced in English.

They are - [æ a: o o:].

3. When the highest part of the tongue occupies the position intermediate between the close and the open one *mid* vowels are pronounced only in English. They are - [e Λ ə: ə].

According to the vertical position of the tongue in Uzbek vowels are divided into narrow, mid and broad:

	narrow	mid	broad
Uzbek	[i, u]	[e, o, o']	[a]

When the lips are neutral or spread the vowels are called *unrounded*. They are - [i:], [i], [e], [æ], [a:], [Λ], [ə:], [ə] in English. In Uzbek they are - [i], [e], [a].

When the lips are drawn together so that the opening between them is more or less round the vowel is called *rounded*.

They are - [o o: u u:] in English.

In Uzbek [u], [o'], [o].

According to *the length*, English vowels are classified into short and long: Long vowels are - [i: a: o: u: ə:]

Short vowels are - [i, e, o, u, Λ, ə].

But in comparison with English, there is no such division of vowels in Uzbek.

Prof. U.K. Yusupov describes some Uzbek geminis vowels such as [shuur, matbaa, so`lim], which are alien to English. He classifies lacuna vowels in the compared languages as follows:

English lacuna vowels for Uzbek: [æ], [u:], [ə:], [a:], [ou], [oi], [ə:], [au], [iə], [uə], [εə], [ai].

There is only one Uzbek lacuna vowel for English. It is [o'].

There is ongoing debate on the phonemic validity of English diphthongs. The two parts that are closely merged together to form diphthongs are complicated entities. The length of diphthongs is the same as that of English long vowels, and they are syllabically indivisible. There are no diphthongs in Uzbek; simply combinations of sounds that have two vigorous and distinct tones. The first component of an English diphthong is a strong, identifiable nucleus, while the second component is a very faint, indistinct glide. The typological analysis aims at describing structural units, i.e. phonemes which function as formal items in the

identification and distinction of words and morphemes.

In comparing **the consonant systems** of two languages, it is suitable to begin with the inventories of phonemes set up in both languages. The inventory of the English consonants consist of 24 phonemes.

[p], [b], [t], [d], [k], [g], [m], [n], [ŋ], [f], [v], [θ], [ð], [s], [z], [ʃ], [ʒ], [h], [tʃ], [dʒ], [j], [w], [r], [l].

The inventory of the Uzbek consonants consist of 25 phonemes.

[b], [v], [g], [d], [j], [(dj)], [z], [y], [k], [l], [m], [n], [p], [q], [r], [s], [t], [f], [x], [ch], [sh], [g`], [h], [(ts)], [ng].

The consonant system of compared languages is classified according to the articulatory and acoustic features.

The general phonetic principles of classification of consonants in compared languages are as follows:

- a.) The place of articulation
- b.) the manner of production;
- c.) the presence or absence of voice;
- d.) the position of the soft palate;

Similarity and differences between them can be seen in the tables below:

The place of articulation	
English	Uzbek
bilabial	labial
Labiodentals	Lingual
dental	Glottal
Alveolar	
Postalveolar	
Palatal	
Velar	
Uvular	
Pharyngeal	
Glottal	
Retroflex	

According to the presence or absence of voice, in both languages there are voiced and voiceless consonants. Moreover, the position of the soft palate are in the same division in compared languages: sonorant and noise consonant.

The manner of production	
English	Uzbek

Occlusive	Explosive
constrictive (fricative)	Affricates
occlusive- constrictive (affricates)	implosive
Rolled	Nasal
	Vibrant

Professor U. Yusupov differentiates some consonants in the following way. The English consonants [t] and [d] are alveolar speech sounds, whereas their Uzbek counterparts [t] and [d] are dental ones. The English [w], in contrast with Uzbek [v], is pronounced with protruded lips. Also, in Uzbek, the voiced consonants [b] and [d] become voiceless at the end of words, which is alien to English: *maktab-maktap*.

The consonants [θ, ð, w] can't be found in Uzbek. Likewise, the Uzbek consonants [x, g', q] do not exist in English.

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